

IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN MANAGEMENT METHODS AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES TO ENSURE ENFORCEMENT OF PUBLIC SAFETY LAWS

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Abstract. The article provides a comprehensive analysis of the issues related to implementing modern management methods and innovative technologies in the activities of internal affairs bodies to ensure the enforcement of public safety laws. Additionally, as a result of the study, proposals and recommendations aimed at improving scientific-theoretical foundations, legislation, and practical activities in the field have been developed.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, innovative management, modern management methods, innovative technologies, public safety, ensuring law enforcement, digital technology.

In the context of administrative reforms, during the period of fundamental changes aimed at modernizing and reforming the country, ensuring openness and transparency, social partnership, accountability, as well as public control in the activities of state administration bodies, one of the urgent issues is to scientifically research and improve the theoretical and practical aspects of implementing modern management methods and innovative technologies in the activities of internal affairs bodies.

At the same time, the pressing tasks of today include further strengthening scientific and technical capabilities, increasing the importance of science in solving urgent problems of socio-economic development, and expanding significant research and innovation processes.

In one of his speeches, the head of our state, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, also noted: "Currently, fierce competition is becoming increasingly intense on a global scale. In such difficult conditions, we must continuously work on the widespread introduction of modern scientific and innovative achievements."

Because this issue is currently becoming a decisive factor in raising the well-being of the population, sustainable development of all spheres of state and public life, and building the bright future of our Homeland" [3].

The growing threats and contradictions in the world, threats to the peace and tranquility of the people, the pandemic, natural and man-made disasters impose on responsible state structures the task of further improving their activities based on the priority idea "All efforts are for the sake of human dignity."

In the context of increasing and intensifying threats in various forms, maintaining peace and tranquility in society, ensuring the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of every member of society remains one of the most urgent and complex tasks of the state, in particular, the internal affairs bodies. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 "On Measures to Raise the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety, Prevention of Offenses and

Combating Crime to a Qualitatively New Level" provides for the implementation of these tasks through the introduction of fundamentally new approaches and mechanisms.

As can be seen from the content of the Decree, the implementation of comprehensive measures is required to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies to a qualitatively new level in the following interconnected areas: a) ensuring public safety; b) preventing offenses; c) combating crime.

This document approved a "road map" for the further improvement of the system of internal affairs bodies, the main directions of which are defined as: firstly, the implementation of organizational changes to further improve the activities of internal affairs bodies, taking into account modern threats; secondly, the widespread introduction of digital and modern information technologies into the activities of internal affairs bodies.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 "On Measures to Raise the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime to a Qualitatively New Level," as well as in order to further develop the system of ensuring public safety in the country and determine the prospective directions of state policy in this area, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2021 No. UP-27 "On Approving the Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Measures for its Implementation" was adopted.

Clause 37 of the Strategy for the Development of the Public Security System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2021 No. UP-27, provides for the establishment of effective mechanisms for prioritizing issues aimed at solving urgent problems in the practice of ensuring public safety, as well as Clause 47 of the Strategy for the Development of the Public Security System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025, provides for the formation and implementation of targeted fundamental, applied, and innovative projects within the framework of the state order for research work in the field of solving problems in ensuring public safety and combating crime.

Also, in order to ensure public safety, the formation of an integrated system for the prevention of offenses and the fight against crime, the establishment of effective activities of internal affairs bodies from the lowest level to the republican level, and the introduction of modern working methods, the following completely new procedures and mechanisms for organizing the activities of internal affairs bodies are being introduced in the country to strengthen law and order and legality, and to ensure peace and tranquility of the population[1].

These include:

firstly, solving problems related to the prevention of offenses and combating crime directly on the ground by identifying and eliminating the causes of crime in the context of each mahalla, family, and individual;

secondly, based on the state of crime in the regions, the division of each district, city, and mahalla into categories and the involvement of all necessary forces and means to eliminate "hotbeds of crime" in cooperation with khokimiyats, sectors, and the public;

thirdly, ensuring peace and stability in the country through the introduction of integrated management and continuous control mechanisms based on the "republic - region -

district - mahalla" system, effective coordination of the activities of internal affairs bodies and other state bodies to ensure public safety;

fourthly, creating a modern image of internal affairs officers, increasing their responsibility and professional potential, forming the necessary skills to combat new forms of crime, and achieving full digitalization of the sphere.

For this purpose, a number of innovative projects and developments have been implemented in the activities of internal affairs bodies over the past short period. In particular, unique new concepts such as "safe city," "safe capital," "safe tourism," "road safety," "safe home," "safe neighborhood," "safe street," "E-community safety," "city inspector," and "rural inspector" are being implemented[4].

In paragraph 3 of the "Strategy for the Development of the Public Security System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025," approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2021 No. UP-27, the digitalization of the public security system is envisaged.

To minimize the human factor in the activities of the service by increasing it to 90%, paragraph 91 sets the task of maximizing the reduction of paperwork in the field of ensuring public safety and increasing the share of documents maintained exclusively in electronic form to 90%[2].

Within the framework of this task, the Public Security Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in cooperation with sectoral services, has developed 66 electronic information systems and modules, bringing the digitalization indicator to 86 percent.

Today, increasing the effectiveness of management in internal affairs bodies, developing a methodology for organizing, coordinating, and controlling its information-analytical and executive discipline activities is of great importance. In this regard, I.T. Korogodin characterizes methodology as a set of methods of scientific knowledge used to reveal important foundations, methods, and approaches to learning[5]. A.M. Orekhov emphasizes that "methodology is a system of principles, methods, and procedures applied in a certain field of knowledge" [6].

In the world, there are international independent structures engaged in organizational, analytical, and control activities, which prepare relevant analytical data not only on the basis of state orders, but also on the basis of orders from private sector representatives. Such independent structures are called "think tanks." International think tanks include the RAND Corporation, the Club of Rome, the Brookings Institution, Chatham House (UK), the Carnegie Foundation, Transparency International, and others[7]. This is of great importance in studying current and prospective trends in the fight against crime, crime prevention, and ensuring public safety.

In the world, a number of methods are used to strengthen information-analytical and executive discipline in the activities of internal affairs bodies (police or militia). In particular, in the organization of information and analytical activities in the police departments of developed countries, the USA, Canada, Japan, Great Britain, France, the Federal Republic of Germany, the Russian Federation, the People's Republic of China, and the Republic of Turkey, the position of "criminologist" ("criminal analyst") has been introduced for collecting, systematizing, analyzing, and forecasting information on the operational situation in the service area, the introduction of economic theory, mathematical methodology, and electronic

computing technology in analysis and forecasting, as well as training professional personnel in the field, studying and analyzing crimes in the nomenclature of police positions.

When introducing modern management methods and innovative technologies into the activities of internal affairs bodies, the following is proposed:

1. It is proposed to create a working group consisting of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and other interested state bodies to prepare a single draft "Public Security Code" of the Republic of Uzbekistan by combining the norms and provisions of more than 200 regulatory legal and departmental regulatory documents in the field of public safety.

2. Development and implementation in the remote control activities of internal affairs bodies of the unified automated information system "E-jamoat xavfsizligi," providing for the "electronic system of internal affairs bodies for ensuring public safety, providing for restrictions on persons under preventive registration, administrative supervision and probationary supervision, as well as the scope of obligations assigned to them and ensuring their observance."

3. Development of the "Methodology for Using the Geocriminogenic Electronic System in Ensuring Public Safety" and ensuring its implementation in the activities of internal affairs bodies to ensure public safety. Studies show that in developed foreign countries, geoinformation systems are widely used not only in social, but also in economic, environmental, security, natural resource management, and scientific fields. In many countries, unique experience in this area has been formed, and positive results are currently being achieved.

4. It is necessary to develop and implement a special monitoring system "Launcher," aimed at increasing the effectiveness of professional training of internal affairs officers in the field of ensuring public safety. According to research, the implementation of this system a) will allow employees to improve their legal, spiritual, educational, and service knowledge by taking mandatory tests daily; b) will allow employees of public security units of the internal affairs bodies (PSB, GUV, JTSX, Probation) to control a total of about 19,000 modern tablet devices distributed in a single window; c) will increase the security of personal and service data and the mobility of tablet device use; d) will provide all subordinate employees of the republic with immediate mandatory familiarization with regulatory documents in their field, as well as instructions from the leadership of the agency and ministry.

5. Development of a drone platform (national special software for drones) based on the "UzFace" video monitoring system, uniting all drones into a single control system, and implementation of drone monitoring. Through this platform, it is possible: a) to keep records and register all drones, analyze who, when, where, and for how long launched them, and block their flight in an area where launching is impossible; b) to remotely automatically control drones, automatically call another nearby drone and return to its charging station when its power is exhausted; c) to patrol any area, independently monitor a designated vehicle and a person, and transmit information online to the Monitoring Control Center about the direction of their movement.

6. Taking measures to organize internships for personnel in the field of organizational and analytical activities of internal affairs bodies, as well as for professors and teachers of educational institutions specializing in their training, in prestigious "Brainstorming Centers" of foreign countries. This will allow for the provision of professional personnel with modern

approaches and knowledge in the effective organization and management of the activities of internal affairs bodies.

The implementation of the above-mentioned measures will serve to increase the effectiveness of organizing and ensuring the implementation of laws on public safety.

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